

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURE 2

Supplemental figure 2. Development of a PBPK-MechKiM model of OAT1 involvement in renal PAH clearance.

To develop the PBPK model for PAH using MechKiM, we made the following assumptions, with justifications to follow: (i) PAH is excreted exclusively by the kidney as the parent compound, by glomerular filtration and tubular secretion, with no other elimination pathways; (ii) OAT1 represents the only uptake step for PAH into renal tubule cells; (iii) there is transporter-mediated efflux of PAH into the renal tubule lumen; (iv) there is no appreciable passive diffusion of PAH across the basolateral or apical membranes of tubule cells, and no appreciable reabsorption occurs.

First, the majority of PAH is eliminated in the urine as the parent compound, and only a small percentage of the dose (~10%) is excreted into the urine as acetyl-PAH (Prescott et al., 1993; Dowling et al., 2001). Also, acetyl-PAH is actively secreted by renal tubules, and has been suggested to compete with PAH for the secretory process – likely due to shared transport mechanisms (i.e., OAT1) (Dowling et al., 2001). That is, elevated plasma concentrations of PAH

reduce the renal clearance of acetyl-PAH (Dowling et al., 2001). Second, although OAT1 and OAT3 represent the major pathways for organic anion uptake across the basolateral membrane of renal tubule cells (Pelis and Wright, 2011), PAH is a preferred substrate of OAT1 over OAT3 (Tahara et al., 2006). Third, MRP2 and MRP4 are organic anion efflux transporters expressed in the apical membranes of renal tubule cells, which likely contribute to PAH efflux into the tubule lumen (Smeets et al., 2004). Finally, PAH is hydrophilic, and therefore, its passive diffusion across biological membranes should be negligible, as we observe in *In vitro* studies. Additionally, tubular reabsorption appears to have a limited role in the renal clearance of drugs that undergo active renal tubular secretion (Mathialagan et al., 2017).

In the next simulations we used the MechKiM model and added OAT1 at the basolateral membrane and an efflux pathway at the apical membrane (i.e., MRP). Given the low passive permeability of PAH, we assumed the intrinsic clearance across the basolateral and apical membranes due to passive diffusion to be zero. For the OAT1-mediated intrinsic uptake clearance ($CL_{int,uptake}$), the value obtained at the 15 sec time point ($5.5 \mu\text{l} \cdot \text{min}^{-1} \cdot \text{million cells}^{-1}$) was used. In addition to an *in vitro* intrinsic clearance value, the MechKiM model requires input of a relative activity factor (RAF) value for *in vitro-in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE) of transport activity. The RAF value corrects for several factors including: (i) differences in transport protein abundance *in vitro* compared to *in vivo*, (ii) *in vitro-in vivo* differences in transport energetics, and (iii) uncertainty regarding the number of tubule cells per gram kidney required for scaling *in vitro* data. Given these unknowns, we initially set the RAF value for uptake to one. Also, the intrinsic clearance ($CL_{int,efflux}$) and RAF value for the efflux pathway were set to $1 \mu\text{l} \cdot \text{min}^{-1} \cdot \text{million cells}^{-1}$ and one, respectively. Using these values, the simulated AUC was over-predictive of the observed AUC (**A**; Hirata-Dulas et al. 1994 and Prescott et al. 1993), indicating an under-prediction of the simulated renal clearance of PAH. To account for this, the $CL_{int,uptake}$ was fixed to $5.5 \mu\text{l} \cdot \text{min}^{-1} \cdot \text{million cells}^{-1}$, and then ‘parameter estimation’ was used to determine the appropriate RAF value for OAT1, in order to recover the simulated renal clearance of PAH – that value was thirty (RAF = 30). Using the $CL_{int,uptake}$ value at the 15 sec time point, and a RAF = 30, the simulated and observed plasma concentration-time profiles for PAH were in good agreement with each other (**B**). Importantly, “Sensitivity Analysis” indicated that PAH clearance, C_{max} and AUC were insensitive to 100-fold changes in $CL_{int,efflux}$ values, but very sensitive to changes $CL_{int,uptake}$ values (data not shown), indicating that the intrinsic clearance and RAF values for uptake and efflux in the final model were appropriate. Indeed, experimental evidence from several studies strongly suggest that the basolateral uptake step is the rate-determining step in renal tubular organic anion secretion (Chatsudthipong and Dantzler, 1991; 1992; Watanabe et al., 2009). To further support the validity of our model for its proposed use, the simulated versus observed cumulative urinary excretion-time profile for PAH when using these final MechKiM input parameters were almost exact (**C**; Prescott et al. 1993).